

Table 1: Quantitative and Qualitative Sample

Survey Type	Sampling Type	Survey Population	Sample
Quantitative survey	Simple random	IDW	1015
Qualitative survey	Purposive	Spouses	25
		Women victims of violence	11
		NGOs (ASMADE, INTERSOS, OCADES, Médecins Sans Frontières)	04
		Social Action	01
TOTAL			1056

Source: Field survey, October 2023

Table 2: Professional Status of IDW

Professional Status	Frequency	Percentage
Farmer	522	51.4
Homemaker	227	22.4
Trader	203	20.0
Student	22	2.2
Seamstress	12	1.2
Gardener	7	0.7
Hairdresser	6	0.6
Artisan	5	0.5
Community health aide	4	0.4
University student	4	0.4
Total	1,015	100.0

Source: Field survey, October 2023

Table 3: Number of Dependent Children by Marital Status of IDW

Number of dependent children	None	1-3	4-6	7-9	10-12	13-19	Total	Freq	P%
Single	43	18	1	2	0	0	64	64	6.3
Cohabiting	2	15	7	2	1	1	28	28	2.8
Divorced	0	3	4	2	1	0	10	10	1.0
Married	32	224	355	122	23	3	759	759	74.8
Widow	3	23	79	40	9	0	154	154	15.2
Total	80	283	446	168	34	4	1,015	1,015	100

Source: Field survey, October 2023

Table 4: Pearson correlations between year of displacement and types of violence

Type of Violence	Correlation Coefficient (<i>r</i>)	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Physical	0.0738	0.0186	Significant correlation (<i>p</i> < 0.05)
Psychological	0.072	0.0219	Significant correlation (<i>p</i> < 0.05)
Sexual	-0.0172	0.5834	No significant correlation
Economic	0.0103	0.7432	No significant correlation
Verbal	0.0198	0.5285	No significant correlation
Social (exclusion, rejection)	-0.0498	0.1126	No significant correlation

Source: Field survey, October 2023; IBM SPSS 20

Table 5: Pearson correlations among types of violence

Type of Violence	Physical	Psychological	Sexual	Economic	Verbal	Social
Physical	1	0.5006	0.1915	0.2331	0.4297	0.2113
Psychological	0.5006	1	-0.0075	0.1968	0.286	0.2818
Sexual	0.1915	-0.0075	1	-0.03	0.1724	-0.0238
Economic	0.2331	0.1968	-0.03	1	0.1098	0.2188
Verbal	0.4297	0.286	0.1724	0.1098	1	-0.0118
Social	0.2113	0.2818	-0.0238	0.2188	-0.0118	1

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 6: Human losses before and during forced displacement

Did you lose a family member during the attack	Frequency	Percentage
No	545	53.7
Yes	470	46.3
Total	1,015	100.0

Source: Field survey, October 2023

Table 7: Type of relationship with victims

Relationship with Victim	Frequency	Percentage
Spouse	97	17.45
Child	111	19.96
Parent	122	21.94
Brother/sister	144	25.90
Others	82	14.75
Total	556	100.00

Source: Field survey, October 2023

Testimonies of Internally Displaced Women (IDW) in the Commune of Dédougou (Burkina Faso)

*Theme: Types of Violence Experienced by Internally Displaced Women
Qualitative Data Collection :Dédougou, Burkina Faso*

Testimony :Respondent 1

The respondent is an internally displaced woman originally from Douroula. She testifies about the circumstances that led to her displacement to the commune of Dédougou.

What was the main reason for your arrival in Dédougou?

The principal cause of my displacement was the terrorist attacks in the Douroula area. We were subjected to various forms of violence as a result of these events, particularly severe psychological violence. In my presence, the terrorists threw my half-brothers into a well. I also witnessed the sudden death of my sister. These events continue to traumatise me deeply on a psychological level.

Furthermore, the armed men returned to massacre a group of people in a place of worship. They opened fire on worshippers: some lost their lives, others lost the use of their legs. I managed to escape by hiding under a tree. Our material possessions and domestic animals were also taken or killed.

I also suffered verbal violence that was particularly difficult to bear. Along the road, the terrorists deliberately humiliated us by making us cry in silence, unable to call for help, stripping us of our clothing in the rain. All of these events took a heavy toll on our psychological and social well-being.

Faced with this unbearable situation, the family sought the assistance of a local authority, including through traditional rituals intended to appease the spirits of relatives who perished in the terrorist attack. The administrative authorities also provided us with food, health-related, and moral support. Their presence was regular upon our arrival; currently, their assistance is more occasional.

Testimony :Respondent 2

Type of violence experienced: physical and psychological.

One day, a group of armed individuals came to our village and ordered us to leave, then departed. Not knowing what to do, we had previously sent some of our belongings to a neighbouring village. After some time without seeing them again, they returned one night and began shooting, claiming they had already warned us to leave. They seized young men and murdered them. Fortunately, my husband, my children, and I managed to flee and took refuge in the village where we had sent our belongings. We stayed there for a few days, but this did not last long, as the armed men came to drive the population out of that village as well, for unknown reasons. This time, we fled with nothing at all, and it was thus that we arrived in Dédougou. During the journey, we encountered these armed men who subjected us to violence and even attempted to take my sons away with them. It was only through persistent supplication, and by the grace of God, that they finally allowed my children to rejoin us.

Since my arrival here, I have received no assistance whatsoever and I am managing on my own, trying to forget these events. It is very difficult, as the slightest unusual sound immediately triggers panic. Just yesterday, during a visit by certain authorities, the sight of the vehicles and the soldiers was enough to send me into a state of intense fear.

Testimony :Respondent 3

Theme: Types of violence experienced by internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

The terrorists entered our village in the evening and began shooting in all directions. We left the village with nothing. During the flight, the terrorists killed my father and my husband along the road. I did not know what to do. Life had lost all meaning for me, as I had never imagined being confronted with such horrors.

Along the road, my four children were crying and asking for food. I could do nothing for them and I began crying myself, overwhelmed by distress. By the grace of God, upon reaching a village whose name I can no longer recall, a woman helped us by giving us food. But that very same night, the terrorists came to attack us again. We set off once more and arrived in Dédougou the following morning.

The nights were impossible to endure; even during the day, I could find no peace. Losing two loved ones at once :my father and my husband :is not something one easily overcomes. It is thanks to the advice of my neighbours, who encouraged me to place everything in God's hands, that I have been able to cope. Today, the situation has improved slightly: I can sleep and eat, even if nothing is truly simple.

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Testimony :Respondent 4

Theme: Violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

The respondent is a 39-year-old widow, originally from the village of Wakara in the commune of Bondoukuy. She lost her husband during the terrorist attacks of 2023, along with two of her children and a cousin during the flight. It was impossible for her to attend the funerals of those she lost: each person had fallen where they lay, amid the general chaos. The journey to Dédougou was extremely long and gruelling, with no means of transport available. She was forced to travel through the bush by day, rest and sometimes sleep under the open sky at night, and resume walking at dawn until she reached Ouarkoye.

It was in Ouarkoye that she received help from relatives. A few days later, as the mayor's office, inspection services, security forces, and the entire population of Ouarkoye were being threatened, she decided to make her way to Dédougou as quickly as possible, hoping to remain there until peace was restored. Upon arriving in Dédougou, housing was not a concern, as her husband already owned a built compound there. Her main difficulties lay in her psychological trauma and her lack of resources to provide for her two daughters and son. She decided to work, initially sweeping the streets to collect gravel and sell it, then gradually developing a small trading business. Today, she is managing relatively well. Her dearest wish is to return to her village in peace once security is restored in the country.

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Testimony :Respondent 5

Type of interview: qualitative.

Had you already experienced violence before your displacement?

Before our displacement and before this security crisis, we lived peacefully with our husbands and children. Personally, the only form of hardship I had known was the exhaustion of farm

work. Everything was fine until the onset of this crisis. Previously, we thought such things only happened to others; we heard about terrorist attacks in other villages and never imagined the same scenario would unfold in our own community.

Did you experience violence during your displacement? If so, could you tell us about it?

I come from the village of Diédougou and I am 37 years old. The eve of our displacement was a Tuesday when armed groups :terrorists :arrived in our village and began shooting everywhere. That day was a black day for the entire village: everyone they encountered was either slaughtered or shot. It was absolutely horrific; bodies lay strewn across the ground. They then gave us a 24-hour ultimatum to leave the village, ordering us to be gone by Wednesday morning. The following day, there was total chaos. My children and I fled, terrified and physically assaulted, making our way towards the nearest town to seek safety. During the flight, we suffered further violence: no one could carry their belongings or food; we were crammed into a tricycle, exhausted and starving, with nothing but tears to shed. My children were profoundly traumatised.

What violence did you experience after your displacement?

Eventually, we arrived in Dédougou, each of us left to fend for ourselves. By evening, I noticed my husband was absent and waited in vain for news of him. I thought he had taken another route. To my great distress, I was told he had not been able to flee and had been shot during the flight. My entire world seemed to collapse: what would become of me and my children? I was living in Sector 6 with no support whatsoever, no one to console me in this time of mourning. On top of grief, we were exposed to hunger. Fortunately, with the help of the Red Cross and UNICEF, we were provided with shelter and some food.

Have you experienced violence since settling here?

After our arrival, a thief attempted to break into my home and tried to force the door open, fortunately without success. It is my faith and my prayers that give me the strength to work hard and feed my children. Life here is not easy, however: the host population does not always make things easier for us and often shows indifference to our situation. My neighbour, in particular, allows his animals to enter my dwelling and cause damage, and I can do nothing about it. Furthermore, here everything is paid for, even water. My prayer at this moment is that God gives strength to our president and that peace returns to our beloved country so that I may go back to my village.

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Testimony :Respondent 6

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

The respondent shares her account as follows: 'We come from the village of Diin. The reason for our displacement to Dédougou was a terrorist attack. It was an evening when the terrorists came to attack us. We fled to reach the town. On the way, we lost two members of our family: our husband and our child. This loss deeply affected us. We fled abandoning our food, our animals, our homes, and all our belongings. We arrived with nothing. At this moment, our hearts weep, but God is great. Thanks to the generosity of certain individuals and the assistance of the mayor's office :in the form of food aid including bags of rice, cooking oil, soap, mats, and tarpaulins :we have been able to manage. The loss of these two family members continues to be very difficult to cope with. Our neighbours in the host community came to us and offered their sincere condolences to help ease our pain in the face of the difficulties we have endured.

Currently, things are going better. We are managing with the support we have received. We can do nothing but pray that the souls of our departed rest in peace and that peace returns to the country.'

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Testimonies :Respondents 7a, 7b and 7c

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

How did you experience violence before the displacement?

Respondent 7a: 'Before our displacement, everything was fine. These individuals would pass through our area without causing any problems, until the day they prevented the people of our village from going to Nouna, a nearby town on which we depended economically. One Wednesday evening, at around 6 p.m., they descended on us with a three-hour ultimatum. That evening was when everything began.'

Respondent 7b: 'Before the forced evacuation of our village, we were compelled to submit to their authority and do everything according to their will. They would take women by force and rape them, amongst other forms of violence. One day, they called a meeting at the market and started shooting people. That was the day of our village's forced evacuation.'

How did you experience violence during the displacement?

Respondent 7c: 'My son, it was not simple. That day was absolute hell. Most of the villagers spent the night in the fields in pitch darkness, and others made their way to neighbouring villages. The following day, once the terrorists had gone, we came back to retrieve our belongings. On that very same day, one man was killed by a landmine and died on the spot.'

Respondent 7b: 'I myself nearly lost my mind, as they killed my husband and two of my sons. My daughters and I managed to escape because men were the primary targets.'

How did you experience violence after the displacement?

After the displacement, the situation was no easier, as the village where we had taken refuge was itself displaced two months later. Things are somewhat better here, as we sometimes receive aid from our relatives and from the social welfare office. One of the respondents notes that, since their arrival, they still cannot meet their food needs, as she has seven children to feed.

Did you seek medical or psychological help after these traumatic experiences?

Most answered yes, explaining that it was thanks to their relatives' encouragement regarding the benefits of psychological follow-up that they took that step. Otherwise, they would not have known such support existed. They report that things are going well now.

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Testimony :Respondent 8

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

Based on the information gathered from the respondent, she described how her village was attacked. There were informants within the village who were plotting with the terrorists. One day, these informants were unmasked by the villagers, who tried to harm them. They escaped and sought the help of the terrorists. This is how the village was indirectly attacked: the terrorists first came under the pretext of holding a meeting with the village men, then opened fire during

this gathering to eliminate all those present. They then dispersed throughout the village to kill the other men who had not attended the meeting.

Facing this situation, everyone fled, carrying children and the elderly in carts along with some belongings and animals. The journey lasted three days before reaching Dédougou. Along the way, children and animals suffered from thirst and hunger. Some villagers died before reaching the town. Men who had managed to escape had disguised themselves as women :wearing veils and hijabs :and had pierced the ears of young boys and made them wear veils to avoid being identified.

Upon arriving in Dédougou, they had nowhere to go and were met with contempt from part of the population. Hunger and exhaustion compounded their isolation, worsened by the loss of husbands and sons. A few days after their arrival, some women died from the trauma they had sustained. With the help of a few well-meaning individuals, they were able to gradually integrate into the town. Since their arrival and up to the present day, they have never received assistance from the social welfare office or any other structure. Every day they go, there is nothing for them. Exhausted by fruitless visits, they now fend for themselves, mainly by collecting gravel to sell in order to cover food and rent expenses. Some children are not enrolled in school due to a lack of financial means.

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Testimony :Respondent 9

Some time ago, in our village of Bourasso, shortly before Ramadan, we heard that a recruitment drive had been organised for young men to defend the country. I encouraged my two sons to participate, unaware that it was a trap. After their names were registered, the recruiters returned the day after the celebration and began shooting throughout the village. We attempted to flee, but at the village exit, unidentified armed men were waiting with a list of all those who had volunteered for the defence of the homeland. They checked the identity cards of each young person wishing to pass and killed all those whose names appeared on their list. When I arrived with my two sons, their names were found on the list. I tried to negotiate, in vain, and both my sons were killed.

Overwhelmed by unbearable grief, I fainted. When I regained consciousness, I found myself beside the lifeless bodies of my children. I had no choice but to continue alone, and it was thus that I found myself in Dédougou. Since that day, I have been suffering alone. I hold myself responsible for my children's deaths. Their father also disappeared during the flight and I do not even know whether he is still alive. To alleviate my pain, I attend prayer sessions at a church and treat myself with plant bark remedies, as I have no money to see a doctor. I have never received aid from any public institution or NGO and I am managing entirely on my own.

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Testimonies :Respondents 10a, 10b and 10c

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

Respondent 10a: I am from Lanfièra. One evening, the terrorists came to our village and began shooting. They told us not to harbour people from Guiédougou. Personally, I lost five members of my family; two people were burnt alive in our home. Seized with fear, we tried to flee towards Dédougou. Along the way, other people were killed. I currently feel very sad and life weighs heavily on me. Upon arriving here, I felt I was suffering psychologically. My

neighbours took me to see a psychologist to help me recover a little. One can never be as before. We pray that the situation improves.'

Respondent 10b: 'I lost my father on the road: he was transporting our belongings to Dédougou when he was attacked. In addition, I lost my three children, who were seized right in front of me, bound, and shot. As a mother, I felt wretched for my children, but I no longer had the strength to intervene. I currently suffer physically and economically. Some people look at me as though I am mad, and I have no one to help me. I did not approach the authorities; it is the words of my neighbours that consoled me. Having accepted that life is not eternal, I consoled myself.'

Respondent 10c: 'I no longer consider myself a full person. I live merely to survive. If suicide were not a crime, I would have already done it. In my family, I lost twelve people in a single day: my husband, my children, and my husband's brother. The terrorists came one morning to seize every man and kill them. My husband and one of my sons had gone to the river; they went after them and killed them there. I did not even see their bodies. I live alone here. I went to the social welfare office for help, but they told me to bring our canton chief before my name could be registered. After extensive and fruitless efforts, I eventually gave up.'

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Testimony :Respondent 11

During our displacement, we experienced psychological, physical, moral, and economic violence. When the terrorists attacked the village, the head of our household was killed. Once we arrived in Dédougou, the shock was so profound that, when we sat down, we struggled to believe we were actually there. At nightfall, we could not close our eyes; the image of our husband was imprinted everywhere in our minds. As for food, even the most basic :a simple cup of tea :was beyond our reach to stave off hunger. The situation was dire: the terrorists had taken or burnt everything we owned. Our children were crying everywhere from hunger, and we could do nothing.

Since settling in Dédougou, we went regularly to the social welfare office, never receiving anything in return :not even a bowl of rice. We then summoned our courage and went door to door offering to wash laundry or help with farm work. The money earned was used to buy food, and sometimes we would ask people to give us food directly rather than money; occasionally, out of pity, they gave us both money and food, along with some second-hand clothing for our children. We managed as best we could with these resources. Because of all this violence, our children's schooling was interrupted; they could not follow their lessons as they could not afford the school fees. They would come home in tears, saying that if their father had been there, none of this would have happened. We, who were responsible for them, hid our own pain in silence to console them. We faced all of this through prayer and the encouraging words of those around us who tried to lift our spirits. We also turned to structures such as the social welfare office and the Red Cross, but in vain :we received nothing from them.

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Testimony :Respondent 12

The respondent is a 40-year-old widow, mother of seven children, a farmer, originally from Diédougou.

The attack was carried out without warning. One day, soldiers came to our village and our children ran towards them in a show of obedience. After they left, armed groups returned to

threaten us, reproaching us for obeying the soldiers more than them, and then departed. It was the day after the Tabaski celebration that these armed groups returned and began destroying our fields. In the afternoon, they opened fire on the population, targeting the men in particular. Some managed to flee; others unfortunately perished. The toll was immense. We women, with no one left to turn to, decided to take a few provisions and items of clothing to flee. But along the way, we were stopped by these same men, who seized and burnt our supplies. It was then that they abducted my co-wife's son and killed him; we were unable to bury him. We walked from Diédougou to Dédougou with no one to help us. Since my arrival here, I received assistance from the social welfare office for three months, in the form of food and accommodation.'

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Testimony :Respondent 13

'The jihadists settled in our village. Initially, they recommended that all women wear the boubou, to which we complied. They then forbade us from playing music or making noise in the village. This affected me greatly, as I could no longer find inner peace. Subsequently, they demanded the wearing of black boubous, and any woman who refused was beaten in front of her husband. If the woman claimed her husband had not bought one for her, the husband would also be beaten by the jihadists. One day, an explosion was heard, killing a jihadist who was based in a school. The following day, they came to accuse us of having alerted the Defence and Security Forces to have them killed. As a result, the jihadists gave us a three-day ultimatum to leave the village. Personally, I cycled 50 kilometres to reach Dédougou. I arrived with nothing. I received no particular assistance apart from housing provided by a non-governmental organisation. Men and women also came to visit and speak with us, which helped me cope with the ordeal. I have six children to care for, whom I struggle to feed. The International Red Cross assists me by covering the cost of medicines for myself and my children.'

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Testimony: Respondent 14

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

On the day the terrorists arrived in our village, they convened a meeting. During this meeting, they laid down their rules: women were no longer permitted to brew dolo (sorghum beer), they had to wear full-length garments accompanied by a veil down to their feet, and were to style their hair simply, without hair extensions or additions. As for men, they were forbidden from playing football and were required to trim the hems of their trousers.

During ceremonies such as weddings or celebrations, only a small number of people were allowed to participate, and there was neither dancing nor music, as gatherings and noise were prohibited. Our various celebrations therefore took place without any festivity. We were obliged to comply with all these rules if we wished to cultivate our fields to feed our families. Any transgression led to immediate reprisals: the terrorists would come to cause trouble and threatened to expel anyone who refused to obey their laws.

Women who continued to brew dolo were beaten, their brew was poured out, and their clay pots were broken. They were warned that the next time, they would be slaughtered rather than flogged. In order to monitor the population and ensure compliance with their rules, they placed informants in the village. In the event of any breach, these informants would alert their superiors to intervene.

We were truly living in a prison, without the freedom to do as we wished. We prayed to God for our defence and security forces to come to our rescue.

When they learned that the security forces were approaching to liberate us, they withdrew. We thought our ordeal was over, but they had merely gone into hiding to regroup. Upon their return, they resumed killing civilians, despite having previously claimed that their war was solely against the government and did not concern civilians.

When the terrorists attacked the neighbouring village, we also fled to reach Dédougou. During the flight, some of our young men were seized along the road by the terrorists, and to this day we have had no news of them.

This crisis has left a deep mark on us. We still cannot forget it. The slightest sound makes our hearts race, so deeply has this ordeal been imprinted in our minds. During our time in Dédougou, our neighbours have provided support through advice and food. We have ultimately entrusted everything to God. We pray that peace will return so that we may go back to our home communities. Life in Dédougou is far from simple, as everything must be paid for. We suffer greatly and the memory of these events remains vivid in our hearts.

Testimony: Respondent 15

Theme: Violence against internally displaced women in the city of Dédougou.

According to the testimony of a displaced woman originally from Lema, the violence she endured caused her severe mental disturbance. Her husband and sons were abducted. It was one morning, as they were preparing to go to the bush, that a neighbour came anxiously to warn her husband that strangers had entered the village and were gathering the men and young boys under the palaver tree.

Before this woman had finished speaking, two young men with cloth-covered faces appeared, shouting the names of the husband and his sons, ordering them to follow immediately. The woman tried to go inside the house to collect some money and a piece of fabric, but was told that if she entered, she would not come back out. She fled, terrified.

Although 57 years old, she ran all the way to Dédougou without even realising the distance she had covered. Along the way, she passed women she knew, but no one spoke to another; each was trying to save her own life. Upon arriving in Dédougou, she was taken in by her brother. On the first day, she could not utter a word; she simply wept. It was only the following day that she tried to explain what had happened, still in tears. She also went more than three days without sleeping or eating.

It was through the consolation of her brother and other people that the situation gradually improved. Her sister-in-law gave her a few items of clothing to change into. Her brother also found her traditional remedies, without which she might not have survived. According to information received two days after the displacement, all the abducted men had been killed and thrown into wells, others left in the open. This news devastated her further. With her brother's help, things have since improved. She remains, however, unable to stop thinking about these events throughout the day. The situation continues to be very difficult.

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Testimony :Respondent 16

The respondent is a 35-year-old married woman, mother of four, originally from the village of Korin.

'Before our displacement, in the village of Korin, we lived well. But since the terrorists arrived, every day was marked by fear: we never knew whether we would survive. They came to our village almost every day to threaten the inhabitants by making us listen to religious sermons. Every night, I could not sleep. One day, at around ten in the morning, the terrorists came and assembled all the village inhabitants; by that time, most of the men had already fled. They lined us up intending to shoot us, but by the grace of God, one of them said to let the women go. They then ordered us to run for two kilometres without stopping, on pain of being shot. I was carrying an eighteen-month-old child in my arms; I ran with him until they left and let us go.

Upon our arrival in Dédougou, finding accommodation was difficult and food was scarce. At one point, I had a dispute with my husband, who then drove me from the home. The conflict arose because a member of my family had passed away and I had asked my husband's permission to attend the funeral; he refused, and I went without his consent. I shared this problem with several people, but it remains unresolved to this day.'

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Testimony :Respondent 17

The respondent is originally from Gassan, married, mother of three children. She arrived in Dédougou the previous year.

How is life on the site?

'Here at the site, we have not received any food for a long time. Schooling our children is very difficult: one dropped out and another came back because the teacher had asked for school fees to be paid. There is nothing to eat, and no land to cultivate. Look at my hands :they are injured from collecting weeds. Here, we have neither land to cultivate nor space to raise animals. Here is the only sheep I bought with a view to reselling it. You can see the henhouse; if only we had the means to buy chicks. Where we came from, there were associations and structures offering credit. After the rainy season, we would trade. I had even bought a cart with its accessories, which the children use to collect sand. It is because of all this that I lost everything and arrived here with nothing. The other day, I went to buy sugar and coffee to try to resell them. It is truly difficult. When I think about all of this, it hurts, but since we are alive, we hope that things will get better.'

Have you considered other solutions given the difficulty of life here?

'One day, when it was said the road could be used, I went via Koudougou to return to the village. When I arrived, I found my house and everything inside had been completely burnt. The walls were blackened beyond recognition. No one can live there any more; it would need to be entirely rebuilt. When I think about that, it is deeply painful. The other day, I fell and my children helped me up; I went to the hospital and the medicines are inside.'

A final word?

'Our prayer is that God brings back peace so that everyone can return home.'

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Testimony :Respondent 18

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

1. What was the main cause of your displacement?

Our displacement was caused by a terrorist attack in 2023.

2. How did your displacement unfold?

Our displacement was very difficult. The terrorists arrived suddenly to harass us; we had no time to take anything with us :neither food nor clothing. In addition, my children and I became separated. It was the following day that we found one another again in Dédougou.

3. Did you lose one or more family members?

Yes, I lost my husband during this attack, as the terrorists were killing only men.

4. Did your displacement take a long time?

Our displacement was swift. The terrorists arrived in the village that same evening and began gathering the men at the mosque to impose their rules on them. In the end, they killed these men, and it was in this massacre that my husband lost his life.

5. How are you currently coping with this difficult situation?

It is currently difficult when I think of my husband's death and everything we lost :the animals, the food, our farming land. But with the support of my relatives, prayer, and the presence of my children, I am managing to find a measure of peace.

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Testimony :Respondent 19

Theme: Types of violence experienced by internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

During the displacement of the respondent's village, terrorist groups had come to warn the inhabitants not to use a certain road. One day, armed groups arrived and committed acts of physical violence and issued threats. They began firing shots, causing widespread panic. They stopped people by force, seized the population's animals, destroyed shops, took sacks of rice and drums of oil, and burnt millet stored in granaries to deprive the inhabitants of food. They also forced every individual they encountered to go to the mosque to pray, then shot at them, resulting in the deaths of several family members, including the respondent's husband's brother and a relative, which deeply affected her psychologically.

In the face of all these events, she remained silent and continues to live with these traumas. She prays for the day she can return to her home community and resume her farming activities. Upon their arrival, representatives of the State came to speak with them, encouraging them to overcome the past violence and find peace of mind. Relatives also visited to offer their support. Finally, State authorities and NGOs provided them with aid in the form of food supplies (bags of maize, beans, and rice), temporary housing (plank-built structures), water jerrycans, and mats. She concludes by expressing her constant prayer to one day be able to return to her village.

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Testimony :Respondent 20

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

What types of violence did you encounter during your displacement?

During our displacement, we were confronted with several types of violence. In terms of physical violence, we were assaulted by terrorist armed groups who took all the food we had,

our money, and our means of transport. They killed many people in our village. Personally, I lost my husband and two of my children. Neighbours also died along the way, and others were abducted :we have had no news of them since. We also suffered verbal violence :insults and threats :as well as psychological violence: humiliation, discrimination, and mistreatment. Men were mistreated along the road; some were slaughtered in front of us, others thrown into wells.

How have you coped with these different forms of violence?

I was deeply traumatised by my husband's death. Even if I could not change anything, the pain was immense. My main problem today remains food. I beg for what I can to feed my two daughters and myself. The donations distributed by social welfare agents have never reached me; every time I go, I am told my turn has passed, and this has been the case from the very beginning. Regarding my health, when I fell ill after my arrival here, I was treated free of charge at the hospital. I thank God; things are better today.

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Testimony :Respondent 21

The interview was conducted with an internally displaced woman in Dédougou.

How do you manage to live with all the violence you have experienced? How do you cope with it?

Respondent 21: 'Through prayer, silence, and the moral support of my relatives.'

Have you seen a psychologist for your mental health?

Respondent 21: 'A psychologist? No. I barely have enough to eat. I do not have the means to see a psychologist.'

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Testimony :Respondent 22

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

Violence experienced by a displaced woman from the village of Youlou.

'We were attacked one evening from around 4 p.m., in a completely unexpected manner, while some community members were in the fields and others at home. Gunfire engulfed the entire village. The population scattered, as did various families. Some of our family members :the family head and his two sons :have still not been found. Some threw themselves into a watercourse, others were killed during the attack; the terrorists took some of the village's young men away. There was even a birth on the road, the mother having been forced to hide in the bush to give birth to her baby boy. It was truly far from simple, but by the grace of God, we are here today. We pray to find the other family members; we do not know whether they were killed or taken by force. We leave everything in God's hands. Sometimes we have no appetite just from thinking about it. Thanks to our families in Bobo-Dioulasso, Ouagadougou, and here in Dédougou, we received seeds, housing, and clothing. We have not consulted a psychologist or a doctor. We leave everything to God who does as He pleases. 'En bè la lemania, ka a da Allah kan.' We continue to pray for everyone to find the peace of mind to overcome these trials and for peace to return to our countries.'

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Testimony :Respondent 23

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

The respondent is a 25-year-old single woman, mother of one child, originally from the village of Tô in the commune of Toma.

'It was Thursday, 23 October 2023; I was returning from school when I heard gunfire. I rushed home to find out what was happening. Upon arriving, I discovered that my father, my brother-in-law, and some villagers had been wounded in a terrorist attack. That very same evening, my family and I packed our belongings into a cart and set off for Dédougou. We were unable to take everything: food and some animals had to be left behind. This catastrophe caused all the village's inhabitants to flee. It is an unfortunate event that turned my life upside down and plunged me into profound sadness. Upon arriving in Dédougou, I had no accommodation and stayed at the stadium for some time. The support of my friends and family helped me greatly to pull myself together. To this day, even the sound of gunfire makes me tremble, so deeply has this event marked me. In order not to dwell on my misfortune, I strive to continue my daily activities as much as possible, which helps me better manage the situation and maintain calm within my family. Today, by the grace of God, things are much better.'

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Testimony :Respondent 24

Type of violence: experience from the Sourou Valley.

'I come from the Sourou Valley, from a village called Débé. Before the arrival of terrorism, we lived in peace. But since the armed groups arrived, our way of life changed completely. They subjugated us, imposing on us women the wearing of the veil. The day the army arrived in the chief town of our commune, the groups withdrew. We rejoiced at the prospect of returning to our normal lives. The army was based at Dî and conducted patrols in our village. But one evening, in the absence of the army, the terrorists emerged from nowhere and invaded the village. They gathered the men under the pretext of a meeting, then opened fire on the population. They beat the women. Nothing could be heard but detonations, screams, and cries from all directions. They burnt houses, provisions, and everything they could. They took our animals and poultry, leaving us nothing. Everyone ran to save their lives. My husband, my children, and I left the house and ran through the bush until we reached Dî. We abandoned everything: clothing, money, all of it. We fled with only the clothes we were wearing.'

A humanitarian organisation sheltered us for a few days until a convoy departed for Dédougou. We decided to join it. On the day of our arrival in Dédougou, difficulties began immediately: with no resources and no accommodation, we had to stay at the stadium. This experience deeply affected us economically and mentally. During our time at the stadium, I had nightmares every night that deeply disturbed me. My husband could not leave my side at night. At times, I would get up in my sleep and run, and my husband would have to catch me. We had never experienced anything like it, not even in films. These symptoms lasted approximately one month. Thanks to traditional treatments, I regained some equilibrium. Even now, the simple sound of a water sachet bursting brings these painful memories flooding back.

In terms of food, we had nothing left and depended on the State and our relatives. Despite the support of humanitarian aid and our relatives, it was not sufficient, but we have learnt to live with it. After the stadium, we looked for rented accommodation. Paying the rent became a serious problem, as my husband has no work here, and city life is very expensive: everything must be purchased. We manage to survive, but not well. We ask the authorities for greater

support, but the real solution is to return home. Insecurity is the root cause of all of this. We greatly thank the President and the Defence and Security Forces for their efforts in reconquering the national territory. May God Almighty grant them the strength to defeat terrorism, for we are suffering greatly.

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Testimony :Respondent 25

The respondent is a 40-year-old trader, originally from Bouna in the commune of Yé, married with eight children. She was displaced in 2024.

'During the attack, I lost a child. I find it difficult to speak about it. This crisis traumatised me deeply. My relatives tried to console me. I was able to report the facts. Today, I have access to health protection services.'

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Testimony :Respondent 26

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

In recent years, Burkina Faso has been grappling with severe insecurity that has spared no region of the country. In the Bankuy province in particular, this scourge has caused significant human, material, socio-economic, and psychological damage, leading to the displacement of populations from surrounding villages towards the commune of Dédougou. The site for internally displaced persons is located near the private Béthel secondary school.

Based on exchanges with displaced women, it emerges that some have endured all manner of violence :rape, theft, threats, and harassment :during their flight. Once in the host city, they are frequently stigmatised.

Respondent 26 testifies as follows: 'I lived in a small village approximately fifty kilometres from Dédougou with my husband and four children. We lived peacefully until everything changed one Wednesday evening. That day, we had not gone to the fields as there was a naming ceremony at our imam's home. To my great surprise, I saw a group of strangers on motorbikes, armed with military-grade pistols, heading towards the mosque where the ceremony was taking place. I wondered: where have these people come from? What do they want? They dismounted their motorbikes, entered the compounds, and gathered the entire village. After approximately thirty minutes of discourse, they brought out our imam and slit his throat in front of his congregation. They then abducted five men, and unfortunately my husband was among them. My heart was broken. I wept throughout the night. The following morning at first light, we took flight towards Dédougou. During the journey, I lost all the belongings I had managed to gather. Since that day, I have had no news of my husband. I am managing with the help of the social welfare office to feed my children.'

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Testimonies :Respondents 27a and 27b

Respondent 27a: 'Early in the morning, before dawn, gunshots rang out at the entrance to the village. In an instant, the terrorists entered and began shooting all the men. When they shot a man who did not fall, they would bind him and throw him into a well. In a panic, we grabbed our children and tried to leave the village in secret, without food or clothing, walking through

the bush to avoid the road. It was only after passing the neighbouring village that we could use the road. Along the way, terrorists crossed our path, threatened us, and told us to go to Dédougou where we would die. Fear consumed us. We lived in terror. About a week after our arrival in Dédougou, my husband passed away. I know his time had not yet come, but it was everything he had endured that took him. I cannot do anything about it; I pray for him constantly and that he may rest in peace. I did not seek psychological support; I placed everything in God's hands, drew strength from within myself, and consoled myself in order to care for my children. I continue to pray for peace to return.'

Respondent 27b: 'It was an evening, the sun had already set, when gunshots encircled almost the entire village simultaneously. Then the terrorists arrived on motorbikes and began seizing men, binding them and loading them into tricycles. They took my own brother in this way. They warned us that if they found us there the following day, they would kill us all. That is why we fled to come to Dédougou. Since our arrival, we have had no news of my brother; we know he is no longer alive. We wept until we were exhausted and left it in God's hands. Since we have been in Dédougou, we have not sought psychological support; there would be no point :even if we had, it could not bring my brother back. All I wish for now is that my brother's soul rests in peace and that peace returns so that all displaced persons can go back to their villages of origin.'

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Testimony :Respondent 28

1. How did you live through the violence?

I am originally from Saneba. One day, during an attack, I lost my husband. We had four children together and since his death, I have been raising them alone. We had to leave the village because of the repeated attacks. Although we also lost other family members, it was my husband's death that traumatised me the most. It was truly not easy to overcome; the pain was immense. We left the village gripped by fear and trauma, to the extent that we did not have time to gather our belongings. During the journey, we suffered from the high cost of transport, with no resources in hand. We were subjected to threats and other forms of violence. Upon arriving in Souri, we received the support of relatives. Some time later, we were able to go back to retrieve some belongings and food, which helped us further. When the rainy season came, we were given a small plot of land to cultivate. With what little I earn, I manage to feed my children.'

2. Did you see a psychologist to help manage the trauma?

'No, I did not. But through the consolation, presence, and support of my relatives, we have managed, and we now give thanks to God. To conclude, we pray to God that the war may end so that we can return home in peace and try to rebuild our lives.'

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Testimony :Respondent 29

Theme: Types of violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.
Village of origin: Debsé.

I have been a victim of physical and psychological violence. The terrorists would sometimes come to impose their laws, their way of life, and their rules on dress. They also prevented the population from going to the fields and from playing music. They carried out abductions and prevented the population from using the road to leave the village. During these attacks and

abductions, I lost two people who were killed in front of the entire population, and we were powerless to react. Men were the primary targets. Faced with the gravity of the situation, some members of the population left the village. As for me, I looked for ways to flee with my children and it is thus that I took refuge on the internally displaced persons site in Dédougou. These criminals caused immense harm in the village: loss of human lives (men), loss of animals and means of transport. This also created great hardship for women.'

I was traumatised by this situation. I lived in constant fear, and my nights were long and filled with nightmares. Everything was difficult, especially for us women who have children to care for without support. Currently, we face difficulties in terms of healthcare and education: we no longer have the means to send our children to school because of our situation as displaced persons. We face problems related to water, housing, and food, as our numbers far exceed the available accommodation capacity. We also have no access to agricultural land during the rainy season, as we have no connections in the city. This situation is pushing young girls into early marriage in order to help their families. This insecurity exposes us to difficulties at every level of life. I could not receive any treatment for my trauma due to my limited means. My current prayer is that peace returns to our country so that we may go back to our home communities and pursue our various activities in full freedom.'

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Testimony :Respondent 30

The respondent is 24 years old, originally from Koumbara, with no formal schooling, widowed, and mother of three children (two girls and one boy).

In Koumbara, everything was going well. I cultivated onions and earned a decent living. But the day the terrorists entered the village, panic seized everyone. They gathered all the inhabitants and ordered us to leave within three days. But their ultimatum was not genuine: the very next morning, my husband, my children, and I took to the road. My husband had a new motorbike; I took the tow-along motorbike with the children, and he followed on a bicycle, and we advanced as best we could. But a few kilometres from Koumbara, the same terrorists stopped us and demanded our motorbike, bicycle, and money. We handed over everything, but despite this, they slit my husband's throat right in front of me and my children. They then told us to walk to wherever we wanted, otherwise they would burn us. Lost and desperate, I took to the road with my three children and we walked all the way to Dédougou.

Upon our arrival, we went directly to the social welfare office, where we were very warmly received. An officer came to question us and give us advice. We were directed to a school where we stayed for a few days before joining the displaced persons camp in Sector 2 of Dédougou. On arrival, I received health, psychological, and food assistance, but the food aid consisted of a single 25-kilogramme bag of rice, and I have received nothing since. Here in Dédougou, I genuinely feel safe and I am no longer afraid. I have never been a victim of violence since I have been here. But the authorities must think about helping us more, as it is often difficult to have even one meal a day. What I ask for myself and my children is above all food. There is also no work available; if the State could create associations for displaced women and train us in income-generating activities, this would truly help us. Finally, all that I have endured, I leave in God's hands, for He has the final word. I pray every day for peace to return to Burkina Faso, in the name of Jesus Christ. Amen.'

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Testimony :Respondent 31

Theme: Violence against internally displaced women in the commune of Dédougou.

'The cause of my displacement was a terrorist attack. When these unidentified armed men arrived in our village, they initially acted with apparent kindness, without harming anyone. But when it came time to leave, they restricted us to a single route out. We were able to gather our belongings and depart without incident. However, once we were deep in the bush, these men pursued us and, without asking anyone's opinion, began shooting at the young men in the group, as well as at some of our husbands, sparing only the elderly and the women. The number of young men killed was significant. Two of my sons were among the victims. They authorised us women to leave, but without touching any of our belongings. We walked without rest. Upon our arrival in Dédougou, we presented ourselves at the social welfare office. We were well received by the population, who provided psychological support through exchanges. In terms of healthcare, we received free treatment. But from our arrival until today, I have never received any food aid from the authorities. It is thanks to a member of our extended family, a primary school teacher, that I am able to feed myself. I prefer to stop here so as not to let my tears flow.'

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Testimonies :Respondents 32a and 32b

Theme: How have displaced women managed to cope after the violence?

How did you manage your life after displacement here in Dédougou?

Respondent 32a: 'Since our arrival, we made do with the little food we had been able to bring along. A month later, by the grace of God, we received assistance from the NGO World Vision International, which provided us with food supplies that allowed us to get through the year. After this donation, we resumed activities: my husband does manual labour and I sell small condiments by the roadside, as well as at the main market to make a small profit. It was in this way that we were able to leave the makeshift shelters we had built upon arrival, find rented accommodation, enrol our two children in school, and place the other four in vocational training centres :including tailoring and mechanics. We thank the NGOs who helped us.'

Respondent 32b: 'As a result of the terrorist attack, my brother was traumatised, but through our prayers, certain authorities committed to treating him and he is now doing very well. Thanks to our neighbours, we were given land to cultivate and had a good harvest. This year, we were even able to re-enrol our children in school and things are going very well. Even now, if there is any violence between me and my husband, the authorities intervene quickly to help me, as what we experienced has left a deep mark on us all. We were trading in Gassan, selling shoes, and we were able to bring this activity to Dédougou, which allowed us to continue selling. We cannot say that we are living in poverty after the displacement; we are gradually managing.'

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Testimony :Respondent 33

The respondent is a 22-year-old married woman, mother of two children, a former farmer, originally from the village of Sônon. She was displaced in 2024.

The respondent stated that she had been a victim of psychological, physical, and verbal violence perpetrated by the terrorists. The latter came to her village to threaten the women and force them to wear the hijab, threatening serious reprisals for any who refused :including cutting off

their ears. Victims of psychological violence, they could not report the situation to the authorities for fear of being killed, particularly as their village was under the control of these individuals. They therefore kept silent and prayed for the situation to change. She recounts having lost an elder sister during an attack, which deeply traumatised her.

She then explains that she was able to flee the village with others, not without difficulty, as armed individuals made the journey perilous. She eventually settled in Dédougou. Upon arrival, she did not resort to psychological support to treat her trauma; it was the support of her relatives that helped her move on. After settling in, she became a victim of theft: the few belongings she had managed to bring from her village were stolen from her. She believes this was because she was new to the neighbourhood. Faced with this additional economic and psychological violence, she chose to remain silent so as not to expose herself to further reprisals.

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Testimony :Respondent 34

Theme: Gender-based violence against internally displaced women before, during, and after their displacement in Dédougou.

Type of violence: psychological.

The respondent, whose first name is Awa, originally from Bouna, testifies: 'During our displacement here, we did not suffer any direct violence. But before our departure, nearly three years ago, armed individuals came to our village one afternoon and ordered everyone to leave immediately, by that evening at the latest. I was pregnant and almost at full term. My husband judged that we would not be able to keep pace with others in the heat, and decided we would leave around 6 p.m. or 7 p.m. We therefore remained, and at 7 p.m., as we began to walk, my waters broke a few metres from the house. We turned back and shortly afterwards I gave birth. We rested for a few hours, and the following morning, very early, as we were preparing to leave, they arrived at our home demanding to know why we had not yet gone. My husband explained that we had indeed received the order to leave but that I had just given birth and we had been unable to do so in time. They said nothing, but went outside to confer, then one of them returned to order my husband to take the baby, slit its throat, cut it into pieces, and cook it. We were devastated and pleaded in vain. I wept; my husband was so overwhelmed by events he could no longer speak. The worst of it was that after it was cooked, they tried to force us to eat the flesh of our own baby. It was like a nightmare, yet it was real. It was at the moment when, gripped by fear and horror, we were about to serve this so-called 'soup' that the security forces took control of the situation. There were exchanges of fire, but by the grace of God, we came out alive.

Upon our arrival in Dédougou, we received help from the social welfare office, which registered our names and gave us a tent and supplies to help us recover. The following day, a psychologist came to speak with us. People from our village whom we encountered sympathised with our pain. Even as I speak to you now, this story continues to haunt me. At times, I lose my bearings entirely. That is all: it is this ordeal that befell me and my husband.'

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Testimony :Respondent 35

'Before our departure from Débé, the terrorists would come from time to time on market days to gather people and talk to them about religion, seeking to convert them. For us women, we were required to wear the veil; music was prohibited and schoolchildren were no longer allowed

to attend school. A few days later, three of them came to warn the inhabitants not to use the road, but many continued regardless. What frightened us most was when they began carrying out abductions, sometimes taking young men away by force. Then one day, at around 5 p.m., they came to tell the inhabitants that they did not want to find anyone there the following day. Immediately, everyone started to fend for themselves that same evening. My husband and I did everything we could to reach Dédougou with the children, with great difficulty, exhausted and thirsty, accompanied by a few family members. He then went back to retrieve some of our belongings left in the village. Since his departure, we have had no news of him. I do not know whether he is still alive, whether he reached the village, and no one else has heard from him either. This has deeply traumatised me; sometimes I cannot sleep at night and I have nightmares. When we arrived, nurses came to visit us, speak with us, and treat those who had been injured along the way. They encouraged us. As for my husband, it was very hard for me to pull myself together; it is my in-laws and my own parents who sometimes come to our rescue, advise me, and help my children, as I know no one in Dédougou.'

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Testimony :Respondent 36

The respondent is originally from Débé. She arrived in Dédougou two to three years ago with her ailing husband. She has six children.

'We were living peacefully in our village when one day people from the bush :terrorists :came and gathered everyone and began to preach. That was the first time. The second time, they came to say they no longer wanted to see any Christians in the village. The third time, they entered the Catholic church and slit the throats of two people in front of portraits of Mary and Jesus. They then announced that they did not want to find any Christians on their next visit. We Muslims were frightened. We took the opportunity to flee at around 1 a.m., as we were forbidden from leaving. Muslims could not leave the village by day, as they would kill them on the pretext of not having told them to leave. We could not easily hide either, as certain villagers who knew us well were collaborating with these people. Prior to this, they had seized our sheep and oxen and burnt some of our provisions. Upon our arrival in Dédougou, the social welfare agents brought us here and built these tents for us. Since our arrival, we have only been given one bag of rice per household and boreholes have been installed. For everything else, we manage by doing small jobs. My husband is a tailor, but he can no longer work properly since his operation. The little he earns goes entirely towards food, as it is very little. Once, we were summoned to the stadium for filming, with lorries full of provisions, but we received nothing. If a child is ill, we take them to the Red Cross where treatment is free of charge. If we could be helped with food and offered employment, we would be happy. We have no farm here; everything remained in the village. We pray to God that peace and tranquillity return so that we may go back to our villages. There, at least, we lack neither shelter nor food and we do not suffer as much.'

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Testimony :Respondent 37

The respondent is originally from Koumbara. She is a widow, her husband having been killed during the flight. She has two children and arrived at the internally displaced persons site in Sector 2 of Dédougou the previous year.

'The terrorists came to our village to warn us to leave. On the very day we had decided to leave, they returned and opened fire to frighten people. We fled abandoning all our belongings; they burnt our houses and provisions and seized our animals. We tried to take a few food supplies and cooking pots, but other terrorists we encountered along the way took them from us. It was then that they also seized the motorcycles of my husband and my father-in-law, and killed both of them.'

'When we arrived in Dédougou, the authorities provided us with food and mats only at the beginning; after that, everyone was left to fend for themselves. We sometimes go to collect firewood to sell, or offer to wash people's laundry to earn a little money and feed our children. Our living conditions are difficult: often there is not enough food for the children. Without my husband, the situation is even more complicated; if he had been here, he would have found a way to provide for us.'

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Testimony :Respondent 38

The respondent reports: 'It was an evening when the terrorists came to our village of Sanaba. Upon their arrival, they began gathering the villagers at the village market. After the gathering, they demanded that we leave the village as quickly as possible before the following evening. We were in such shock that we did not know where to begin, as we had absolutely not anticipated such a situation. That very evening, we began gathering our belongings to take them to another neighbouring village that the terrorists had not yet reached. The entire village was in turmoil; the sound of weeping filled the air. We had no time to gather all our belongings, as the time allowed was very short. After our displacement, a few days later, my husband returned to the village to retrieve our rams and goats. Unfortunately, he never came back. The same fate befell all the villagers who attempted to return to retrieve their animals: some were killed, others abducted and never seen again. One month later, the terrorists attacked that village as well, without even giving the inhabitants time to leave. On their arrival, they immediately began firing shots throughout the village. It was then that we fled directly to Dédougou, with nothing other than the clothes we were wearing. And we have been here ever since, scraping by to find something to eat. Sometimes we receive donations from associations and other structures. It was truly very painful and to this day we still feel that pain; we live in solitude. But everything God does is good. We have entrusted everything to His hands and will continue to pray for peace to return to our country, Burkina Faso, so that we may return to our various home communities.'

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Testimony :Respondent 39

The respondent is originally from Dankoumana.

'Everything was fine for us until the day a group of terrorists appeared. Their presence changed everything. We were under their control: everything we did depended on them. They dictated their laws. All women were obliged to wear the veil; they directed prayers and everyone was required to follow their orders. Some of them conducted investigations in the village: anyone who spoke ill of them was killed, and anyone who tried to report them to our soldiers was eliminated. They closed the schools. We lived like this with them until the day they decided to expel the entire village. It was in 2022; we did not know where to go. We were unable to gather all our essential belongings and did not have enough means of transport to accommodate

everyone. Children followed the animals on foot; others were loaded into tricycles to reach a destination. In the grip of fear, we had an accident on the road, with injuries. There was also the abduction of a child who was following the animals, and some animals did not survive the journey without grazing. That is how it happened before we arrived in Dédougou. In Dédougou, the injured were hospitalised. Not knowing where to sleep, we spent the night at the stadium, hungry and thirsty. The following morning, the children were crying from hunger. Those who still had a little savings went to find food for their children; others sold their few important belongings at low prices to buy something to eat. We endured this with our children until we were able to access State food aid. Despite this, the hardship did not end: jobless :whereas I had been a trader in my village :we were forced to seek work with the local people of Dédougou, scraping by with what little we earned, trying to enrol our children in school, and so on. Some of our children were forced to work in households to bring in a little money; younger children collected plastic bags and jerricans to sell. That is how we have managed until now. I miss my village greatly. May peace return to the country so that we can go home: that is my deepest wish.'

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Testimony :Respondent 40

The respondent is originally from Soni.

'For years, we lived under terrorist threat. The jihadists imposed the wearing of the veil on all women in our village; anyone who refused was mistreated. We were under their orders, unable to do anything without their consent. They would sometimes forcibly abduct our young men. We lived in sadness and pain.

On 16 April 2023, at around 5 p.m., the jihadists came to order us to leave the village. That day, there was a fuel shortage and we lacked the means of transport to reach a safe city. We loaded a few provisions and belongings into donkey-drawn carts; the children walked with the animals. Given the distance, some animals could not withstand the fatigue and died along the way. We slept in the open bush with hunger and thirst. We arrived in Dédougou without some members of our family. We wept and cried until exhaustion, and to this day we have no news of them. Upon arrival, we had no housing and stayed at the stadium, empty-handed, with no money to rent a room or buy food. It was the government that had these tents constructed for us. It also provided us with food, but we have no money to buy condiments and firewood.

In the mornings, we walk around with the children collecting plastic bags to sell. Today, we are truly exhausted and we are suffering. We pray for our Defence and Security Forces and the Volunteers for the Defence of the Homeland (VDP), who keep watch day and night for our security. We thank the government. May peace return to Burkina Faso so that we can go home and cultivate our fields.'

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Testimony :Respondent 41

Type of interview: structured interview with a displaced woman who lost her husband.

Age: 40. Marital status: widow. Number of children: 4. Residential area: Sector 5.

1. Could you tell me a little about your life before the displacement?

'Before the displacement, we lived in Sadigan. My husband cultivated millet, maize, sesame, and cotton. I sold shoes and clothing. My three children attended school and we lived in peace.'

2. How did your displacement to Dédougou unfold?

'Our displacement was extremely difficult. On the day our village was attacked by the terrorists, we fled on foot with nothing. We made our way towards a neighbouring village, from where we found a taxi that took us to Dédougou.'

3. Could you tell me about the circumstances of your husband's death?

'While we were fleeing, my husband wanted to protect us. Unfortunately, he was struck by a bullet that gravely wounded him. He died on the road and I was unable to bury him, for fear that the terrorists would come back and finish off me and my children. I therefore continued alone with the children.'

4. How has this loss affected your life?

'This loss has greatly weakened me. I am in despair, as it is not easy to live without a husband. Our children are still minors, I have no work, and I must assume all responsibilities alone.'

5. How do you currently provide for your own needs and those of your children?

'I go around homes offering to wash laundry to earn a little money. Sometimes, these people also give me food and clothing so that we can eat and be clothed.'

6. Do you currently receive any assistance from the social welfare office?

'Occasionally, NGOs give us food, soap, and even clothing, but it is not enough.'

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Testimony :Respondent 42

The respondent is a displaced woman from Bourasso, currently living in Sector 5 of Dédougou with her children. She was displaced in 2023 due to insecurity.

The respondent explains that everything began with meetings and threats organised in the village by terrorist armed groups. After multiple threats, the village was attacked, causing many deaths, injuries, and disappearances. During the attack, she lost her husband and two brothers, which caused profound fear and trauma that led to her displacement. After fleeing the village, she arrived in Dédougou empty-handed and was consoled by her relatives, as she was in deep shock. She faced housing difficulties and had nothing to eat, but received help from her circle of acquaintances for food and accommodation. A few days after the tragedy, Defence and Security Forces escorted them back to retrieve their belongings. Having returned to Dédougou with a few possessions, she continued to receive aid intended for displaced persons and from well-meaning individuals. She was suffering and in despair, as her livelihood had been farming and trade, and the displacement had taken everything from her. Through the consolation of those around her and the aid she received, she gradually recovered and resumed trading to provide for her children. She has decided to remain in Dédougou, even after the potential resettlement of her village, in order to continue developing her business.

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Testimony :Respondent 43

'Before our displacement, our village lived in peace, with everyone free to do as they wished. But at some point, terrorist attacks began to threaten the village, causing significant damage: houses, granaries, and other property were set alight. One evening, these individuals came to

shoot in our village and some people lost their lives. They then informed us that they did not want to find anyone in the village within three days. It was truly far from simple for us. We walked approximately 30 kilometres on foot with the children to settle in Dédougou. Upon arrival, we did not know where to sleep. A displaced persons site was established and small houses were constructed for us. Since our arrival, we have been unable to meet our basic needs: we lack food, water, and other essentials. We can say however that today, we thank God Almighty and the Head of State for his assistance to internally displaced persons.'

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Testimony :Respondent 44

The respondent, whose first name is Korotimi, is a 42-year-old displaced woman originally from Bonou. She was a victim of verbal, physical, and sexual violence at the hands of the terrorists.

The terrorists sowed terror and panic in the village, and no one dared speak. They were from the Fulani community within the village. They burnt the public services :the gendarmerie, the mayor's office, the police station :forcing the officers to flee. According to the respondent, the terrorists would regularly come looking for her husband. One day, they came and took both her and her husband into the forest. Her husband remained there for two days. She thought everything was over for him, but by the grace of God and through prayer, he returned two days after his abduction.

At that time, the terrorists were actively looking for people working for the government. One day, as she sat with her four children who were studying in front of her, they burst in without warning and shouted: 'Who told you to attend French school? If we come back and find this education still going on, you know what will happen to you. We will impose the madrasa school on you.' She raised chickens and sold poultry feed, but all of this was left in the village. They killed two police officers, seized equipment from the mayor's office, including school canteen provisions (rice and oil). They killed a child from a neighbouring family, cut off one of his feet, and left it at the youth centre. The neighbour identified the child by his shoe, as he had been warned to stop selling charcoal.

Initially, if a woman did not wear the veil to go to the bush and they caught her, they would follow her home to make her put it on, then force her husband to accompany them to the bush, where they would rape the woman in front of him before abandoning them. They regularly summoned young people, the elderly, and children to ask whether any of their number were VDP members or soldiers; if so, they were to come forward and not return to the village. They also threatened the village chief: if the security forces came to Bonou, it would be catastrophic for the population as they would block access on a radius of two kilometres. On the road to Dédougou, the respondent was not directly threatened, but on that same day people had been killed and their bodies left on that very road. Upon arriving in Dédougou, she went to the social welfare office to explain her situation, but the agents asked her to bring a witness and told her that the displaced persons they had registered came from Guiédougou, not Bonou. Since her displacement, she has received no aid.

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Testimony :Respondent 45

'Before my arrival in Dédougou, which was caused by a terrorist attack, I had already been a victim of domestic violence. I was married to a man in the village; at the beginning of our

marriage, everything was fine and we had three children together. After a few years, my husband began drinking alcohol and, from that point on, everything fell apart in our home. He became very aggressive, particularly in terms of intimate relations. He used multiple means of control: insults, dangerous threats, and physical blows. I suffered greatly with him. This situation had serious consequences for my life: the suffering drove me to leave him, even though I still loved him. I thus lost all ties with his family, who had considered me their own daughter. It also caused deep emotional suffering: stress, loss of self-confidence and self-esteem, to the point of no longer wanting to enter into a relationship with anyone else.

As potential solutions to reduce violence against women, I suggest, in terms of prevention, education on gender equality and awareness-raising. For the support of victims, I propose financial assistance, reception structures, and repressive mechanisms (legislation and sanctions).'

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Testimony :Respondent 46

The respondent is originally from Guiédougou.

'Before they came back to drive us out, they first came to forbid certain practices: no more music playing, no more dolo-brewing, all women had to wear the veil, and no one was to communicate with the Defence and Security Forces about them. They then returned to verify whether their instructions were being followed. Anyone who did not comply was beaten with a whip. After a few weeks, they returned in large numbers and started firing in the village, killing men and even young boys, and burning our grain crops. Everyone ran in all directions; it was impossible to take anything, as saving one's life was the absolute priority.

Once in Dédougou, we faced difficulties with housing and food, but thanks to well-meaning individuals, we received food, money, and a tent to sleep in. These donations have since ceased. Currently, we women are suffering, as we have neither work nor resources. We received no psychological support; health workers came to check on our children, give them medicines, and inform us about child malnutrition, as well as direct us to NGO health centres for free healthcare. We pray every day for this war to end so that we can return to our villages in Guiédougou and live in peace.'

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Testimony :Respondent 47

The respondent is originally from Bao. She is 36 years old.

What type of violence did you suffer at the village?

'The violence I endured in Bao, before arriving here in Dédougou, was the slitting of my son's throat right in front of me, because he had refused to join the terrorists. It was a Wednesday. An unforgettable day; a day when I nearly went mad. I screamed so loudly that the armed groups threatened to burn me alive if I did not stop, and I told them to go ahead and do it. They left and came back on Friday to tell us they did not want to find anyone in the village that afternoon, imposing on us not to pass through Tougan :on pain of death :even though Tougan was the nearest town. At that moment, I was half out of my mind with grief over the death of my only son, for he was the one who cared for me and his six sisters since my husband's death. He left me like an animal, without any funeral rites. I sometimes asked myself why God had created me as a human being if I was to endure such misfortune in my life.'

Did you consult a psychologist, or did anyone provide you with moral support?

'No, because I was my own psychologist. I spoke to myself and consoled myself alone. No one could calm me: my only son, my sole boy who cared for us, was gone. I could do nothing.'

How do you feel now in Dédougou?

'Since I arrived in Dédougou, things have only worsened from day to day. We had nothing to eat. I have been in Dédougou for a year and I have never received any assistance from the social welfare office. Living conditions were difficult; even drinking water was a problem as it had to be purchased. The clothes I am wearing and the shoes on my feet were given to me by my neighbour, as I had brought nothing with me. We did not know what to eat in the mornings; my neighbour would sometimes give me rice to cook for the children. She suggested sending two of my daughters to Ouagadougou to work for her friends and send me a little money, while the other four would remain with me. Each of them sent me 5,000 francs per month. It was not much, but I managed with it, also buying firewood to resell to supplement my income. I will never stop thanking that woman for what she did for me. I can say that it is thanks to her that we are alive today, for if we had depended solely on social welfare assistance, we would no longer be here; I have never received any from them.'

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Testimonies :Respondents 48a and 48b

Theme: Violence experienced during displacement :loss of family members.

Respondent 48a: She lost her husband during the attack, which deeply affected her, as he had been the cornerstone of the family. Overnight, she found herself having to assume both the role of father and mother. This situation weighs heavily on her and she often cannot hold back her tears. Furthermore, it was her daughter who was in a particularly worrying state: the girl would see her father in her dreams at all times, and in some dreams he would call her to come with him. When the mother explained that her father had died, the child's condition would worsen further. She had no means to take her to a hospital. She then sought natural remedies from elderly women she did not know, driven by desperation. Some of them showed her herbal teas to give her daughter. The treatment was followed and the child recovered. However, the youngest child continued to ask for her father, and the mother did not know how to respond. She tried to forget but with the children around, and given how recently they had arrived, it was difficult to let go so quickly. She also received no help from relatives, as support usually comes at the time of funerals, and the family was waiting for peace to return before organising the funeral in the village. For now, she focuses on prayer to find peace of mind and care for her children.

Respondent 48b: She lost three members of her family during the attack :two young men and an elder :and this completely shattered her. According to their traditions, young men who die in such circumstances do not receive the usual funeral rites, and the burial is carried out differently. For the two young men, there were no ceremonies and burial followed specific rituals. For the elder, there was a funeral ceremony with special rites, and on the day of the funeral, the women prepared flatbreads distributed to all those present. These funeral rites ultimately took place in Dédougou, but the respondent was unable to attend, as she was elsewhere with her husband at the time.

Figure 1: Pearson Correlation

Source: Data 2022 and 2023

Figure 2: Recourse facing violence

Source: Field survey, October 2023

Map 1: Area Covered by the Survey

Source: Field survey, October 2023